

Smarandache Summands

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Let $n > k \geq 1$ be two integers. Then a Smarandache Summand is defined as:

$$S(n, k) = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-k \cdot i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} (n-k \cdot i) \quad [\text{for signed numbers}]$$

$$S|n, k| = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-k \cdot i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} |n-k \cdot i| \quad [\text{for absolute value numbers}]$$

which are duals and semi-duals respectively of Smarandacheials.

$S(n, 1)$ and $S(n, 2)$ with corresponding $S|n, 1|$ and $S|n, 2|$ are trivial.

a) In the case $k=3$:

$$S(n, 3) = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-3i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} (n-3i) = n + (n-3) + (n-6) + \dots ; [\text{for signed numbers}].$$

$$S|n, 3| = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-3i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} |n-3i| = n + |n-3| + |n-6| + \dots ; [\text{for absolute value numbers}].$$

Thus $S(7, 3) = 7 + (7-3) + (7-6) + (7-9) + (7-12) = 7 + (4) + (1) + (-2) + (-5) = 5$; [for signed numbers].

Thus $S|7, 3| = 7 + |7-3| + |7-6| + |7-9| + |7-12| = 7 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 5 = 19$; [for absolute value numbers].

The sequence is $S(n, 3)$: 3, 2, 0, 5, 3, 0, 7, 4, 0, 9, 5, 0, ... ; [for signed numbers].

The sequence is $S|n, 3|$: 7, 12, 18, 19, 27, 36, 37, 48, ... ; [for absolute value numbers].

4) In the case $k=4$:

$$S(n, 4) = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-4i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} (n-4i) = n + (n-4) + (n-8) \dots ; [\text{for signed numbers}].$$

$$S|n, 4| = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-4i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} |n-4i| = n + |n-4| + |n-8| \dots ; [\text{for absolute value numbers}].$$

Thus $S(9, 4) = 9+(9-4)+(9-8)+(9-12)+(9-16) = 9+(5)+(1)+(-3)+(-7) = 5$; for signed numbers.

Thus $S|9, 4| = 9+|9-4|+|9-8|+|9-12|+|9-16| = 9+5+1+3+7 = 25$; [for absolute value numbers].

The sequence is $S(n, 4) = 3, 0, 4, 0, 5, 0, 6, 0, 7, 0, 8, 0, 9, 0, 10, 0, 11, \dots$

The sequence is $S|n, 4| = 9, 16, 16, 24, 25, 36, 36, 48, 49, 64, 64, 80, 81, 100, 100, \dots$

5) In the case $k=5$:

$$S(n, 5) = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-5i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} (n-5i) = n+(n-5)+(n-10)\dots$$

$$S|n, 5| = \sum_{\substack{0 < |n-5i| \leq n \\ i=0, 1, 2, \dots}} |n-5i| = n+|n-5|+|n-10|\dots$$

Thus $S(11, 5) = 11+(11-5)+(11-10)+(11-15)+(11-20) = 11+6+1+(-4)+(-9) = 5$.

Thus $S|11, 5| = 11+|11-5|+|11-10|+|11-15|+|11-20| = 11+6+1+4+9 = 31$.

The sequence is $S(n, 5): 3, 6, 2, 6, 0, 5, 10, 3, 9, 0, 7, 14, 4, 12, 0, \dots$

The sequence is $S|n, 5|: 11, 12, 20, 20, 30, 31, 32, 33, 45, 60, 61, 62, 80, 80, 100, \dots$

More general:

Let $n > k \geq 1$ be two integers and $m \geq 0$ another integer.

Then the Generalized Smarandache Summand is defined as:

$$S(n, m, k) = \sum_{i=0, 1, 2, \dots, \text{floor}[(n+m)/k]} (n-k \cdot i) \quad \text{[for signed numbers].}$$

$$S|n, m, k| = \sum_{i=0, 1, 2, \dots, \text{floor}[(n+m)/k]} |n-k \cdot i| \quad \text{[for absolute value numbers].}$$

For examples:

$$\begin{aligned} S(7, 9, 2) &= 7+(7-2)+(7-4)+(7-6)+(7-8)+(7-10)+(7-12)+(7-14)+(7-16) \\ &= 7+(5)+(3)+(1)+(-1)+(-3)+(-5)+(-7)+(-9) = -2. \end{aligned}$$

$$S|7, 3, 2| = 7+|7-2|+|7-4|+|7-6|+|7-8|+|7-10| = 7+5+3+1+1+3 = 20.$$

References:

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